

Audio Transformer for Synthetic Speech Detection via Benford’s Law Distribution Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a novel approach that enhances synthetic speech detection by applying Benford’s law analysis to the encoder embeddings. By leveraging Benford’s Law as supplementary information alongside the existing embeddings, the model gains a detailed understanding of both content-related features and numerical distribution patterns. Our approach demonstrates superior performance on the ASVspoof 2019 LA dataset, achieving an AUC score of 0.921, while providing enhanced interpretability.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**; *Machine learning*; • **Information systems** → **Multimedia information systems**.

KEYWORDS

synthetic speech detection, audio deepfakes, audio transformer, Benford’s law

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1 INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in Text-To-Speech (TTS) and Voice Conversion (VC) technologies have reached an unprecedented level of quality, making it increasingly difficult for human listeners to distinguish between synthetic and natural voices [17]. This capability carries great promise for improving communication, entertainment, and accessibility. However, it also creates huge challenges, particularly regarding the spread of synthetic audio content for malicious purposes, such as disinformation [21]. The deliberate dissemination of false or misleading information using synthetic voices poses a severe risk to societal discourse, media trust, and democratic processes. To counter this, research has focused on developing end-to-end, AI-driven solutions, with significant input from the ASVspoof community [25].

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This community has traditionally focused on spoofing attacks aimed at bypassing automatic speaker verification systems. Yet, the expertise harbored within this community presents a valuable opportunity for broader application, particularly in countering disinformation exploiting synthetic audio. The necessity for such an interdisciplinary strategy becomes evident when considering the evolution of interpretability in related fields, such as image processing. There, techniques like Grad-CAM have successfully enhanced the transparency of decision-making processes by visually highlighting the image regions influencing a model’s predictions [20]. Similar adaptations are needed in audio domain, where current methods borrowed from image analysis lack effectiveness.

However, the pressing need to detect synthetic speech has instead led to the development of approaches which, although effective, often lack interpretability, despite this being a crucial aspect for practitioners in the forensics and the journalistic domains [5].

Therefore, this paper proposes a synthesis detection approach that employs an audio transformer as the foundational encoding architecture, enhanced with a Benford’s law analysis during the prediction phase to check the distribution patterns of input embeddings. This architecture is inspired by the SFAT-Net-2 (Speech Formant Analysis Transformer Network) [4], which achieves synthetic speech detection as a byproduct of attending the input magnitude and phase in order to track the fundamental frequency (f_0).

Traditional architectures like ResNet [8] and SyncNet [3] lack certainty regarding which parts of the spectrogram are pertinent after the training. In contrast, the attention mechanism inherent in transformers offers an effective means to model the intricate relationships between speech harmonics within the input signal. Therefore, similar to [4], we decided to rely on transformers in the spectrum encoding phase.

In the decoding phase, we decided to incorporate a Benford’s Law analysis [1] of the First Digit Distribution (FDD). Benford’s Law has been effectively applied in various fields to detect image tampering [22] and AI-generated images [2]. This paper extends its application to the audio domain, proposing that Benford’s Law analysis, implemented within a transformer architecture, offers a robust framework for spotting irregularities in the numerical distributions of synthetic content.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 explores Benford’s law and its relevance; Section 3 delves into the details of our proposed architecture; Section 5 covers the dataset and training parameters of the experimental setup; Section 6 discusses the evaluation outcome in relation with the existing state of the art; Section 7 presents the ablation study to quantify the impact of the Benford’s law analysis, and Section 8 concludes with a summary and directions for future research.

2 THE IMPORTANCE OF BENFORD'S LAW

Benford's law, also known as the First Digit (FD) law or Significant Digit law, reveals a remarkable statistical phenomenon observed in the leading digits of numbers across a wide array of real-world data (e.g. population figures, stock prices, death rates, and fundamental physical and mathematical constants): According to Benford's law, the likelihood of encountering numbers starting with smaller digits is disproportionately higher than that for larger digits, its frequencies following the logarithmic relation

$$F_a = \log \frac{a+1}{a}, \quad (1)$$

where F_a denotes the frequency of the leading digit $a \in \{1, \dots, 9\}$ [1].

Benford's law transitioned from a curiosity to a robust probabilistic model with broad applicability in analyzing datasets from various domains [18]. It has become particularly valuable in identifying manipulations within datasets, as modified data often deviates from the expected Benford distribution, revealing anomalies [6]. Figure 1 illustrates the expected distribution for datasets adhering to Benford's Law.

Figure 1: Expected FD distribution of non-anomalous sets

The application of Benford's law in highlighting discrepancies has proven indispensable in forensic examinations, aiding in the exposure of fraudulent financial records, counterfeit documents, and manipulated digital media [2, 22, 26]. It has proven to be effective in detecting image tampering [22] and AI-generated images [2]. In a recent study by Mari et al. [13] a novel approach utilizing first-digit statistics for detecting forged audio was introduced, showcasing good performance and low computational complexity. Additionally, Mari et al. [14] proposed a system that utilizes FDD as an embedding, concatenated with short-term long-term, and bicoherence embeddings, to create a fusion model. This fusion model achieved overall superior performances.

The successful application of Benford's Law in many aforementioned scenarios supports the hypothesis that it could equally serve as a robust mechanism for identifying anomalies in synthetic speech—where the statistical properties may diverge from those observed in authentic audio recordings. Moreover, Benford's Law

provides an additional analytical layer that improves the overall efficacy of detection, contributes to a more comprehensive approach to detecting audio manipulation or generation, and is *designed* for improved interpretability.

3 PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Our architecture is composed of 4 components, as shown in Figure 2 and listed below:

- **Magnitude Encoder E_X** : A sequence-to-sequence (seq2seq) transformer designed to convert the magnitude X of an input file into a corresponding sequence of embeddings denoted as y_{enc}^X (Section 3.1).
- **Phase Encoder E_Φ** : A seq2seq transformer designed to convert the phase Φ of an input file into a corresponding sequence of embeddings denoted as y_{enc}^Φ (Section 3.2).
- **Benford's Law module BL** : A module composed by fully-connected layers designed to convert concatenated embedding of magnitude and phase to a probability distribution y_{bl} adhering to Benford's Law (Section 3.3)
- **Synthesis Predictor P** : A seq2seq transformer designed to convert y_{enc} and y_{bl} into a 2-dimensional vector signaling the presence of synthetic speech (Section 3.4).

Figure 2: Proposed architecture for Benford's law analysis

Let X and Φ represent the magnitude and phase of an input recording x , where

$$\begin{aligned} X &\in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M} = \log (|\text{STFT}(x)|), \\ \Phi &\in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M} = \sin (\angle \text{STFT}(x)), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with L representing the number of frames and M representing the number of frequency bins of the short-time Fourier transform $\text{STFT}(\cdot)$.

The initial part of the network, inspired by the SFAT-Net-2 model [4], encodes the input through two loosely coupled encoders, E_X and E_Φ , the outputs of which are concatenated:

$$y_{enc} = E_X(X, \Theta_{enc}) \circ E_\Phi(\Phi, \Theta_{enc}). \quad (3)$$

in which Θ_{enc} denotes the set of model parameters, \circ denotes the column-wise concatenation of the two sub-embeddings.

The resulting input encodings are then fed into the Benford's law module BL , which yields an approximation of the FDD of the input values:

$$y_{bl} = BL(y_{enc}, \Theta_{bl}). \quad (4)$$

with Θ_{bl} being the required set of parameters.

Finally – and crucially, as we will see in Section 6.2 – the concatenation of the Benford's law distribution and the input encodings

y_{enc} is used to predict whether the input audio exhibits an anomalous distribution:

$$\hat{y}_{\text{synth}} = P(y_{\text{enc}} \circ y_{\text{bl}}, \Theta_{\text{bl}}). \quad (5)$$

In the following sections, we will provide a more detailed description of the elements outlined above, including mathematical formulations to highlight the differences between this work and SFAT-Net-2.

3.1 Magnitude Encoder

The magnitude encoder E_X is a seq2seq transformer designed to convert the magnitude X of an input file into a corresponding sequence of embeddings denoted as y_{enc}^X .

Adhering to the methodology outlined in [4], the input magnitude X is initially split into non-overlapping 2D patches x_p^X , subsequently projected into a series of patch embeddings z^X :

$$z^X \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D} = [z_1^X, z_2^X, \dots, z_N^X], \quad (6)$$

where

$$z_p^X = \text{project}(x_p^X, \Theta_{\text{enc}}^X), \quad (7)$$

with Θ_{enc}^X the required set of magnitude encoding parameters.

Subsequently, the magnitude embeddings, y_{enc}^X , are calculated by feeding the sequence with positional information into the transformer T_{enc}^X :

$$y_{\text{enc}}^X = T_{\text{enc}}^X(z^X + z_{\text{pos}}), \quad (8)$$

utilizing z_{pos} as standard learnable 1D positional embeddings.

This transformer consists of alternating layers of multi-headed self-attention (MSA) and multilayer perceptron (MLP) blocks, with layer normalization applied before and residual connections after each block – further details on this can be found in [4].

3.2 Phase Encoder

The phase encoder E_Φ follows the foundational principles and design of E_X , and is therefore a seq2seq transformer designed to convert the phase Φ of an input file into a corresponding sequence of embeddings, denoted as y_{enc}^Φ .

Also in this case, we relied on the the very same procedure presented in [4]: Initially, the input phase ϕ is split into a sequence of non-overlapping 2D patches x_p^Φ , which are projected into a sequence of patch embeddings denoted as z^Φ :

$$z^\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D} = [z_1^\Phi, z_2^\Phi, \dots, z_N^\Phi], \quad (9)$$

where

$$z_p^\Phi = \text{project}(x_p^\Phi, \Theta_{\text{enc}}^\Phi), \quad (10)$$

with Θ_{enc}^Φ being the necessary set of parameters.

Phase embeddings y_{enc}^Φ are then computed by introducing the sequence, along with positional information, to the transformer T_{enc}^Φ :

$$y_{\text{enc}}^\Phi = T_{\text{enc}}^\Phi(z^\Phi + z_{\text{pos}}), \quad (11)$$

featuring a similar composition of alternating layers of MSA and MLP blocks as described in [4].

In order to ensure consistency and to synchronize the input information, we kept using a unique framing grid of N patches in both E_Φ and E_X as well as an identical number of dimensions D , and the very same positional embeddings.

3.3 Benford’s Law Module

The Benford’s law module BL aims at estimating the FDD y_{bl} of the input embeddings $y_{\text{enc}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times D}$, with N indicating the number of patches and D being the dimensionality of the latent space for each patch.

Given the potentially large amount of elements ($N \cdot D$), the input to the module is condensed to a $1 \times D$ vector by averaging across the patch dimensions:

$$y_{\text{bl}}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{N} (\mathbf{1}^t \cdot y_{\text{enc}})^t, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{1} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$ represents a vector comprised entirely of ones, and t denotes the transposition, resulting in $y_{\text{bl}}^{(1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times 1}$.

This condensed input is then processed through two fully-connected layers. The first layer aims to intercept patterns in the input vector and to improve the convergence speed:

$$y_{\text{bl}}^{(2)} = \text{GELU} \left(W_{\text{bl}}^{(1)} \cdot y_{\text{bl}}^{(1)} + b_{\text{bl}}^{(1)} \right), \quad (13)$$

where

$$\text{GELU}(x) = \frac{x}{2} \left(1 + \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^{x/\sqrt{2}} e^{-t^2} dt \right) \quad (14)$$

is the Gaussian Error Linear Unit (GELU) activation function [9], the matrix $W_{\text{bl}}^{(1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{D_{\text{bl}} \times D}$ represents the weights of the linear layer, and $b_{\text{bl}}^{(1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{D_{\text{bl}} \times 1}$ its bias vector.

The second fully-connected layer, instead, aims to reduce the output to 9 dimensions, and to ensure its values lie between 0 and 1:

$$y_{\text{bl}} = \text{sigmoid} \left(W_{\text{bl}}^{(2)} \cdot y_{\text{bl}}^{(2)} + b_{\text{bl}}^{(2)} \right), \quad (15)$$

where

$$\text{sigmoid}(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (16)$$

is the sigmoid activation function [19], and the linear layer is defined by its weight matrix $W_{\text{bl}}^{(2)} \in \mathbb{R}^{9 \times D_{\text{bl}}}$ and bias vector $b_{\text{bl}}^{(2)} \in \mathbb{R}^{9 \times 1}$.

Hence, the Benford’s law module BL is crafted to flexibly capture patterns characteristic of Benford’s Law, while simultaneously avoiding undue complexity with only one additional hyperparameter: the dimension D_{bl} of the hidden layer.

3.4 Synthesis Predictor

The synthesis Predictor P is a seq2seq transformer designed to convert the input embeddings y_{enc} and y_{bl} in an output signaling the presence of synthetic speech:

$$\hat{y}_{\text{synth}} = P(y_{\text{enc}} \circ y_{\text{bl}}, \Theta_{\text{p}}), \quad (17)$$

where \circ denotes the concatenation of the two input embeddings, Θ_{p} represents the model parameters, and $\hat{y}_{\text{synth}} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ realizes a one-hot encoding for synthesis detection:

$$\arg \max \left(\hat{y}_{\text{synth}} \right) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{the input violates Benford’s law} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

The predictor P is identical to the one in SFAT-Net-2 [4]: The input sequence of embeddings of length N is projected to have D^P dimensions, then prepended with a $1 \times D^P$ class token vector, and

lastly transformed by the prediction transformer into a sequence of output embeddings \hat{z}^P .

The first element \hat{z}_0^P of the transformed output sequence is processed by a linear classification layer to yield the final output:

$$\hat{y}_{\text{synth}} = f\left(W_{\text{synth}} \cdot \hat{z}_0^P + b_{\text{synth}}\right), \quad (19)$$

with W_{synth} and b_{synth} being weight matrix and bias vector of the linear classification layer, and $f(\cdot)$ its activation function.

However, it is important to clarify that eq. (17) is indeed ill-defined: At this stage, the encoder embedding y_{enc} is a $P \times D$ sequence, while the Benford's law embedding y_{bl} is a 9×1 vector. To reconcile this mismatch, we propose to project y_{bl} into a $D \times 1$ vector by means of:

$$y_{\text{enc}}^{\text{bl}} = W_{(9 \rightarrow D)} \cdot y_{\text{bl}}, \quad (20)$$

where $W_{(9 \rightarrow D)} \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times 9}$ is a learnt projection matrix. Following the projection, the vector is prepended to the entire sequence of encoder embeddings:

$$\tilde{y}_{\text{enc}} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+1) \times D} = \left[\left(y_{\text{enc}}^{\text{bl}} \right)^t, y_{\text{enc}} \right], \quad (21)$$

where t denotes the transposition. Equation (17) should thus become:

$$\hat{y}_{\text{synth}} = P(\tilde{y}_{\text{enc}}, \Theta_{\text{p}}). \quad (22)$$

4 TRAINING LOSSES

A proper choice of training losses is essential to let the network learn both content-related features and numerical distribution patterns. In this section, we will detail the loss functions for both the Benford's law module, and the final synthesis prediction transformer.

4.1 Benford's Law loss

The goal of the Benford's Law loss is to teach the *BL* module to estimate the First Digit Distribution (FDD) of the embeddings y_{enc} , i.e., a regression task in which the target values represent the frequencies of a probability mass function.

We define y_{bl} as the known embeddings FDD, i.e.

$$y_{\text{bl}} = \text{FDD}(y_{\text{enc}}) = \text{FDD}(E(X, \Phi, \Theta_{\text{enc}})), \quad (23)$$

where Θ_{enc} denote the set of encoding parameters $\Theta_{\text{enc}}^X \cup \Theta_{\text{enc}}^\Phi$, and $E(X, \Phi, \Theta_{\text{enc}})$ the complete encoding function, i.e.,

$$E(X, \Phi, \Theta_{\text{enc}}) = y_{\text{enc}} = E_X(X, \Theta_{\text{enc}}^X) \circ E_\Phi(\Phi, \Theta_{\text{enc}}^\Phi). \quad (24)$$

Furthermore, let us denote with \hat{y}_{bl} the estimated FDD of the encoding embeddings, i.e.:

$$\hat{y}_{\text{bl}} = BF(E(X, \Phi, \Theta_{\text{enc}}), \Theta_{\text{bl}}), \quad (25)$$

where Θ_{bl} are the parameters of the Benford's law module.

At training phase we will ask the network to minimize the Benford's law loss l_{bl} corresponding to

$$l_{\text{bl}}(X, \Phi, y_{\text{bl}} | \Theta_{\text{enc}}, \Theta_{\text{bl}}) = \text{JSD}(y_{\text{bl}} || \hat{y}_{\text{bl}}), \quad (26)$$

where $\text{JSD}(A||B)$ denotes the Jensen-Shannon Divergence (JSD) [15] between two vectors y_{bl} and \hat{y}_{bl} , each one representing a probability mass function.

The JSD, a symmetrized version of the Kullback-Leibler (KL) Divergence [12], is defined by:

$$\text{JSD}(A||B) = \frac{1}{2} \text{KL}(A||M) + \frac{1}{2} \text{KL}(B||M), \quad (27)$$

with $M = \frac{1}{2}(A + B)$ being a mixture distribution of A and B .

The biggest challenge to calculate the loss l_{bl} is the computation of the ground truth FDD vector, since y_{bl} is a function of the encoding network parameters Θ_{enc} , which are varying during the training. The target distribution can be retrieved efficiently by recalling that the first digit d of a real number x is defined by

$$d(x) = \left\lfloor 10^{\log_{10}(x) - \lfloor \log_{10}(x) \rfloor} \right\rfloor, \quad (28)$$

where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor operator.

Given the an input set of real numbers $\{x_1, \dots, x_N\}$, the FDD vector y_{bl} can be retrieved by normalizing the histogram of their respective first digits:

$$y_{\text{bl}} = \frac{1}{N} \text{hist}(d(x_1), d(x_2), \dots, d(x_N)), \quad (29)$$

where the i -th element of y_{bl} corresponds to the frequency of the first digit $d = i$.

4.2 Synthesis Prediction Loss

The goal of the synthesis prediction loss is to teach the transformer P to distinguish between synthetic and natural content, i.e. to perform a classic binary classification task. Therefore, we decided to rely on the standard Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss for our experiments:

$$l_P(X, y_{\text{synth}} | \Theta_{\text{enc}}, \Theta_{\text{p}}, \Theta_{\text{bl}}) = \text{BCE}\left(y_{\text{synth}}, P\left(E(X, \Theta_{\text{enc}}), \Theta_{\text{p}}\right)\right), \quad (30)$$

where Θ_{p} denotes the parameters of the prediction transformer, and the BCE loss is defined by

$$\text{BCE}(y, \hat{y}) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i), \quad (31)$$

with y being the ground truth, \hat{y} the predicted value, and N the number of samples in the dataset.

5 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

5.1 Dataset

All experimental procedures were conducted on the ASVspoof2019 speech dataset [27], specifically curated for the ASVspoof challenge. This dataset encompasses speech utterances intended for comprehensive analysis, targeting both speech spoofing detection and automatic speaker verification tasks.

The ASVspoof2019 dataset includes a Logical Access (LA) set containing a mix of authentic and synthetic voice utterances, categorized into three partitions: *train*, *dev*, and *eval*. Each partition incorporates natural speech signals alongside synthetic speech samples generated through diverse methods. Notably, the *train* and *dev* partitions share a common set of 6 synthesis algorithms (A01, A02,

Table 1: BL-Net Training Configuration

Transformer	Global Parameters		MLP Blocks		Self-Attention Blocks	
	Depth	Embedding Size	Dimensions	Dropout	Number of Heads	Head Dimension
E_X – Spectrogram Encoder	8	512	1024	0	8	64
E_Φ – Spectrogram Decoder	8	512	1024	0	8	64
P – Synthesis Predictor	4	512	1024	0.1	6	64
Multi-layer Component	Hyper-parameters					
BL – Benford’s Law module	hidden layer dimension (D_{bl}) = 9					

..., A06), while the *eval* partition introduces samples generated by 13 distinct techniques (A07, A08, ..., A19). This partitioning simulates an open scenario, mirroring attacks performed with unknown algorithms on unfamiliar voices.

Despite the ASVspoof dataset striving for an equitable distribution of voices, it is acknowledged that the distribution of silent intervals within it exhibits uneven characteristics [16]. To address this, we used the MarbleNet model for voice activity detection [10] to eliminate any leading or trailing silence. Additionally, we normalized the volume of all utterances in accordance with the EBU recommendation on audio signal loudness [7], with a sampling frequency of 16,000 Hz.

For our experiments, we merged the *train* and *dev* partitions into a unified training set, reserving 10% for validation out of this unified training set, and keeping the *eval* partition exclusively for testing purposes.

Without adjustments, the training and test data would exhibit a significant difference in the number of natural and synthetic recordings—6 times more synthetic in training and 13 times more in testing. To counter this imbalance, we employed oversampling of natural recordings during training, achieving a ratio of 1:1. Additionally, a random starting offset was applied to each trial to mitigate the risk of repeated content within single epochs. However, it is acknowledged that this approach, while intended to prevent overfitting, may have unintentionally introduced some undesired bias towards the recording transmission channels [5].

5.2 Training parameters

In Table 1, we detail the training parameters relevant to the transformers employed in our computational processes. The major contributors to the parameter count are the two encoders, E_X and E_Φ . Their extensive parameterization results from a substantial count of alternating pairs of MSA and MLP blocks. This numerical value is specifically referred to as *depth*.

6 PERFORMANCE IN RELATION WITH THE EXISTING STATE OF THE ART

6.1 Evaluation Metrics

In the assessment of model efficacy, two pivotal metrics were employed as evaluative benchmarks: the Equal Error Rate (EER) and the Area Under the Curve (AUC). The EER, a well-established metric in binary classification paradigms, pinpointed the threshold

Figure 3: ROC curves of SotA models on ASVspoof LA 2019

on the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve where the false positive rate aligns with the false negative rate. A diminished EER signified heightened performance, indicative of an equilibrium point where the rates of erroneously accepting genuine samples and incorrectly rejecting impostor samples are harmonized. Complementary to this, the AUC, gauging the area under the ROC curve, furnished a comprehensive evaluation of the model’s discriminatory acumen across diverse threshold values. Elevated AUC values denoted superior overall performance, with the metric ranging between 0 (representative of negligible discriminatory capacity) and 1 (indicative of flawless discrimination).

6.2 Results Overview

Given the challenges associated with data distribution in existing ASVspoof 2019 evaluation subsets, direct comparisons with state-of-the-art methods pose difficulties. We consider SFAT-Net2 [4], RawNet2 [23], RawGAT-ST[24] and AASIST[11] for comparison. All networks were trained from scratch on the pre-processed training and development partitions described in the previous sections, adhering to the hyper-parameters specified by the authors.

The ROC curve, illustrating the performance of our model in relation with the existing state of the art, is shown in Figure 3. The

Table 2: Performance of SotA models

	RawNet-2	RawGAT-ST	AASIST	SFAT-Net2	BL-Net
EER (%)	20.66	23.00	17.10	16.59	16.37
AUC (#)	0.877	0.841	0.896	0.910	0.921

Figure 4: Baseline Architecture 1 (BA1): Transformer for synthetic speech detection

line styles employed herein symbolize good (solid) and intermediate (dotted) performance levels, as explicated in the accompanying Table 2 reporting the AUC and EER metrics. Among these, Our proposed architecture for Benford’s law analysis (named BL-Net for the sake of compactness) emerged as the most proficient performer on the ASVspoof2019 LA test subset, exhibiting the lowest EER (16.36%) and highest AUC (0.921) scores. Remarkably, these results align closely with the performance achieved by SFAT-Net2, despite the lower complexity of our proposal – which does not require to train two additional transformers for spectrogram autoencoding and fundamental frequency tracking.

7 ABLATION STUDY

In our ablation study, we conducted two experiments to investigate the impact of incorporating BL into the synthesis prediction process.

7.1 Experiments

In the first experiment, we aimed to understand if the BL analysis did bring any benefit to the detection performance, or not. Therefore, we designed a first baseline architecture BA1, depicted in Figure 4, in which the embeddings derived from the magnitude and phase encoders are combined and subsequently transmitted to the synthesis predictor, which is responsible for determining if the input speech is synthetic or not.

In the second experiment, we explored whether incorporating BL into a multi-task learning framework could provide an advantage over our proposed network topology. We therefore designed a second baseline architecture BA2, illustrated in Figure 5, where the magnitude and phase embeddings are combined and fed simultaneously into the BL module and the synthesis predictor. BA2 demonstrates the role of estimating Benford’s law embeddings as an auxiliary branch, acting as a steering wheel to ensure it captures underlying Benford’s Law distribution to aid in synthetic speech detection. In this sense, the architecture is very similar to the one used by the authors of SFAT-Net-2 [4].

Table 3: Outcome of the ablation study

	Baseline(BA1)	Byproduct(BA2)	BL-Net
EER (%)	20.26	17.00	16.37
AUC (#)	0.884	0.911	0.921

Figure 6: ROC curves of ablation study on ASVspoof LA 2019

7.2 Results

The results of the ablation study against the ASVSpooF 2019 evaluation subset are shown in Figure 6 and outlined in Table 3. Our proposed architecture BL-Net and BA2 both exhibit a significant improvement over the baseline model BA1, indicating a notable enhancement in synthetic speech detection resulting from the integration of BL analysis.

The proposed topology of BL-Net, however, achieves a higher AUC (0.921) compared to the other two models, positioning it as the optimal method for integrating BL into a synthetic speech detection pipeline.

8 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This paper introduces a novel approach to synthetic speech detection based on an audio transformer, which incorporates a Benford’s

Law analysis during the prediction phase to examine the distribution patterns of input embeddings. This method enhances synthetic speech detection performance by capturing essential numerical patterns in the input data, and providing a nuanced understanding of expected distribution patterns. The paper also details Benford's law module structure and the related Benford's Law loss. The experimental results confirm superior performance in synthetic speech detection compared to existing methods, with BL-Net proving to be the most effective approach.

Looking ahead, we plan to advance our research by refining existing models and developing new ones that capitalize on Benford's Law more effectively. This may involve optimizing model architectures, diversifying learning strategies, and experimenting with various data representations. Moreover, we plan to evaluate robustness against global interference tactics, such as lossy encoding and injection of background noise.

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